

DEVELOPMENT OF A CONTROL SYSTEM IN THE ATMOSPHERIC BLOCK OF THE PRIMARY OIL REFINING UNIT TO ENSURE THE QUALITY OF OIL FRACTIONS**Aygun Safarova Agamirza,***Associate professor,**Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University***Elvin Abasli Namiq***Master of the Azerbaijan State**Oil and Industry University***Abstract**

Technological complex of primary oil refining, since the technological process operates under a very heavy load, if we approach this system from the point of view of ensuring the conditions associated with satisfying the quality indicators of the obtained oil fractions under conditions of high temperature and wide changes in consumption and indicators quality of raw materials, the control system should belong to the class of large and complex systems. Ensuring the implementation of this technological process in both safe and cost-effective modes, as a rule, largely depends on the level of its automation system. In our opinion, the use of higher quality automatic control systems based on the latest achievements in this field of science, providing both potential outputs and standard indicators of the quality of oil fractions produced on the basis of new modern technical means used during the period of modernization in these facilities, is very relevant.

Keywords: technological process, oil refining, control system, adaptive system, distillation column

In the oil refining industry, after tube furnaces, distillation columns are considered one of the devices that can operate at the expense of high energy costs in the production process. Based on this, the problem of minimizing the energy costs required in the production of products in distillation boilers has been one of the main issues of interest to researchers for many years. However, in these distillation boilers, mainly in their cubic part, large-scale research work to minimize energy costs in general in the production process almost always did not give the expected results. Basically, according to experts, the problems in the field of development and application of control systems, mainly ensuring the minimization of energy consumption in fractionating boilers, are mainly in the fact that they always operate mainly under the influence of internal and external exciting factors and that their dynamic characteristics are mostly non-linear, and also due to their non-stationarity. In this regard, it is necessary to highlight the work done to address the above issues. In all studies carried out with the aim of minimizing energy consumption in the production process in simple fractionation coils, the issue of control in these process devices has been formalized as a robust issue. But even here, when developing a control system that has more stable and efficient indicators in production conditions in distillation columns, reliance on control technology in a new form of modern control can give almost the best results. [1-3]

As you know, in conditions where the consumption of raw materials and its quality indicators over a wide range, mainly in all distillation columns, as well as in atmospheric columns and the absence of analyzers that automatically determine the quality indicators of

the target products obtained, there are traditional automatic control systems that ensure the producing of product fractions with stable quality indicators, often fail, which in principle makes it impossible to process and use.

In the research work, it is planned to mainly use the combined control system in solving the problems of optimizing the atmospheric block and optimal control of the technological complex for primary oil refining. As we have shown, the main principle of operation of this control system is to compensate for the consumption of crude oil processed in the atmospheric unit, as well as excitatory factors that may arise due to changes in quality indicators, before they affect the quality indicators of oil. received fractions. This compensation is provided by a proportional change in the temperature of the product entering the selected plate, or a given irrigation rate [4,5].

As is known, in the main application of such control systems, maintaining a stable temperature regime inside the cube in the tank is one of the most important conditions. Experience has shown that changing the temperature on a plate below the selected plate, for whatever reason, can in turn cause almost certain problems in the application of such a control system. For all these reasons, it is more expedient to take into account the change in the temperature regime in the lower part of the selected plate when calculating the corrective signal in the proposed control systems and increase the stability of the control system. [6-8]. Thus, at the top of column k-2, depending on the exciting effects created in the proposed temperature control system, the new temperature set-point will basically be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{T}_{yy}^{cari} \in T_{yy}^0 \\ T_{yux}^{cari} = T_{yux}^{tap} \pm \varepsilon \end{cases} \quad \text{then} \quad P_k = 0; \quad \tilde{T}_{yux}^{tap} = T_{yux}^{tap} \tag{1}$$

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{T}_{yy}^{cari} \geq T_{yy}^0 \\ T_{yux}^{cari} \geq T_{yux}^{tap} \pm \varepsilon \end{cases} \quad \text{then} \quad P_k = C_F(t) \frac{\Delta F_{sluv}}{2}; \quad \tilde{T}_{yux}^{tap} = T_{yux}^{tap} + P_k \tag{2}$$

Here, $\tilde{T}_{yy}^{cari}$ – the current value of the temperature in the k-6 column, T_{yux}^{tap} – the command

value of the temperature mainly in the top of the column, T_{yux}^{cari} – the current value of the temperature mainly in the top of the column, T_{yy}^0 – the range of temperature changes that can be mainly released on the k-6 column, ε – based on the correction signal in the regulation system shows the inclination of temperature.

In order to be able to ensure the production of fractions with even more stable quality indicators in the atmospheric block, the figure of the self-configurable regulation system, which mainly includes the combined regulation system mentioned above, is shown in Fig.1.

This is how the labor activity of the control system is built: basically, when the time of transition to a new technological regime or the consumption of raw materials change their quality indicators, with the help of a

comprehensive program at the above level, firstly, it is mainly checked how adequately the mathematical models reflect the current technological situation, and, if necessary, the operational adaptation of mathematical models is carried out.

Then, using of various optimization algorithms, the optimal operating mode of the technological device is calculated based on the new situation. The obtained mode is sent to the lower level due to its stabilization in the device based on the command given by the operator-technologist.

In general, the central server is mainly designed for operational management of plant production. It is considered that in both cases, keeping the temperature regime basically stable in the below is one of the main conditions.

Fig. 1. The scheme of the adaptive control system for atmospheric column

The proposed regulation system mainly ensures that the quantity of the flow entering the atmospheric column meets the standard requirements of its quality indicators, mainly produced product fractions at any values of its quality indicators. This type of system can work in the case of a priori information scarcity, adjusts its activity indicators through adaptation due to changing external and internal influences.

Based on the results of such a system, it can ensure the production of fractions with stable quality indicators, regardless of the exciting effects that may occur in the technological system.

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